

Corrosion of aluminium, zinc and mild-steel in an industrial atmosphere

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Corrosion rate of metals, atmospheric salinity and sulphation rate have been determined at Vapi Industrial Complex situated in South Gujarat. Monthly corrosion rate is in the order of aluminium < zinc < mild-steel (MS); whereas yearly rate follows the same trend. Mild-steel exposed vertically suffer less corrosion than those exposed at an angle of 45°.

Atmospheric corrosion is the most wide-spread form of metal deterioration which affects man-made metallic structures and also influences a nation's economic health. The atmospheric corrosion processes have been studied in many places around the world¹.

The most important climatic factors on the corrosion process are the relative humidity, sunshine hours, temperature of the air and the metal surface, wind velocity, duration and frequency of the rain, dew and fog. The latter is related to the layer formation which is influenced by the relative humidity². Sulphur compounds and chlorides ions are the most common and important atmospheric corrosive agents have been reported³.

In India, data regarding the relative corrosivity of atmospheres at various cities⁴⁻⁸ are available along with that in U.K., U.S.A. and other European countries⁹.

The present study was undertaken at Vapi industrial complex (Dist. Valsad) of South Gujarat. The site is characterized by high pollution, high rainfall, high humidities, high temperature with greater fluctuations in diurnal temperature.

Results and discussion

Meteorological parameters : Generally, the rain starts in June and continues upto October. Total annual rainfall was measured as 6070 mm in 1995 and 4901 mm in the year 1996. Relative humidity and temperature data of maximum and minimum of the year 1995 and 1996 are shown in Fig. 1. It was found that December, January and February are considered to be the cold months, whereas March, April, May and June are the hot months of the year (Average maximum and minimum temperature are about 306 and 299 K, respectively).

The fact that sulphur dioxide plays a major role in the corrosion of metals. Sulphation rate was measured ranging

Fig. 1. Temperature (in K) and relative humidity (in %).

from 28 to 65 mg/sq. dm/month (Fig. 2). A sulphation rate of 0.9 mg SO₃/sq.dm/month is usually accepted as representative of clean air¹⁰. Sulphation rate was reported from 10 to 40 mg SO₃/sq.dm/month at Baroda⁵. 30 to 90 mg SO₃/sq.dm/month at Ankleshwar⁶ and 13 to 51 mg SO₃/sq.dm/month at Surat⁷ industrial area.

Atmospheric salinity rate was found ranging from 17 to 40 mg NaCl/sq.dm/month (Fig. 2). Salinity rate ranging from 5.1 to 32.1 mg NaCl/sq. dm/month at Patan¹¹ and 3.9 mg/m².d chloride (average 6 months) at Cuba have been reported¹².

Fig. 2. Sulphation rate (in mg SO₃/sq.dm/month) and atmospheric salinity rate (in mg NaCl/sq.dm/month).

Aluminium : The corrosion rate of aluminium was found very low compared to mild-steel and zinc. Monthly corrosion rate of Al was found in range of 3 to 15 (1.3 to 6.7 $\mu\text{m}/\text{y}$) mg/sq.dm; whereas yearly corrosion rate was found in range of 55 to 131 (2 to 4.8 $\mu\text{m}/\text{y}$) mg/sq.dm (Fig. 3). Al in outdoor exposure is attributed with the formation of more protective oxide film on the metal surface which might have offered protection to the metal from reacting with the surrounding environment.

Average seasonal corrosion loss of Al in rainy months (44 mg/sq.dm) is 2.6 times higher compared to the values obtained in summer months (17 mg/sq.dm) (Table 1).

Fig. 3. Monthly and yearly corrosion rate of aluminium and zinc under outdoor exposure during different months.

Monthly corrosion rate of Al indicates a weak correlation with (i) atmospheric salinity rate ($r = 0.13$), (ii) maximum relative humidity ($r = 0.15$) as well as with satisfactory correlation with sulphation ($r = 0.38$). No correlation appeared to exist between corrosion rate of Al and temperature.

Zinc : Monthly corrosion rate of zinc was found in the range of 20 to 119 (3.4 to 20.3 $\mu\text{m}/\text{y}$) mg/sq.dm; whereas yearly corrosion rate was found in the range of 173 to 268 (2.4 to 3.8 $\mu\text{m}/\text{y}$) mg/sq.dm (Fig. 3). The type of corrosion on zinc plate is attacked uniformly. Monthly exposures of maximum corrosion is observed in the month of August and September and minimum corrosion is observed in March and April. As pointed out earlier, the maximum corrosion observed where the pollution values also high.

Table 1. Average seasonal corrosion rate (in mg/sq.dm)

Metals	Season (1995-96)		
	Rainy	Winter	Summer
Al	44	33	17
Zn	389	309	171
MS	7230	5466	2553

Average seasonal corrosion rate of zinc plate in rainy months (389 mg/sq.dm) is higher compared to the value obtained in winter months (309 mg/sq.dm) and hot months (171 mg/sq.dm) (Table 1). Monthly corrosion rate of zinc indicates a satisfactory correlation with sulphation rate ($r = 0.45$) and weak correlation with atmospheric salinity rate ($r = 0.23$). No correlation appeared to exist between temperature and corrosion rate of zinc.

Mild-steel : Monthly corrosion rate of mild steel (MS) was found in the range of 335 to 2200 (58 to 382 $\mu\text{m}/\text{y}$) mg/sq.dm; whereas yearly corrosion rate was found in the range of 11500 to 20076 (164 to 287 $\mu\text{m}/\text{y}$) mg/sq.dm (Fig. 4). The corrosion suffered by a MS was mainly of a general type. Approximately 2 mm thick corrosion product was formed on panels of twelve months exposure.

Average seasonal corrosion rate of MS in rainy months is 1.3 to 2.8 times higher compared to the values obtained

Fig. 4. Monthly and yearly corrosion rate of mild steel under outdoor exposure during different months.

in winter months and summer months. Panels of MS exposed in rainy months initially developed a tiny yellow spots within a week which turns reddish-yellow then orange-brown and finally black in colour after three months exposure period. Higher corrosion rate in rainy months are attributed to the corrosion product which is washed regularly by rain keeping fresh metal surface exposed to further corrosion. Lower corrosion rate in summer months are due to removal of gaseous and particulate pollutants from the atmosphere by higher wind velocity. Monthly corrosion rate of MS indicates a significant correlation with salinity rate ($r = 0.36$) as well as with partial positive correlation with sulphation rate ($r = 0.49$) and a weak correlation with maximum relative humidity ($r = 0.29$).

Positional effect : The result indicates that the panels exposed vertically suffer less corrosion than those exposed

at an angle of 45°. Average value of corrosion rate was 617 mg/sq.dm/month in vertical position and 1240 mg/sq.dm/month at angle of 45° position (Table 2). The reason undoubtedly being the retention of moisture and atmospheric particles for longer periods on a panels exposed at an angle of 45°.

Table 2. Positional effect on corrosion rate of mild-steel

Month	Rate of corrosion in mg/sq.dm	
	Vertical	At 45°
1996		
April	332	675
May	299	603
June	465	940
July	794	1600
August	889	1790
September	780	1577
October	760	1500

Comparison of monthly corrosion rate : MS : Zn corrosion loss ratio is not constant and varies from a low of 12 to a high of 26; MS : Al corrosion loss ratio varies from a low of 111 to a high of 300 and Zn : Al corrosion loss ratio varies from a low of 7 to a high of 15.

Experimental

Corrosion rate of MS, Zn and Al plates were determined in an industrial atmosphere of Vapi in outdoor conditions. The test plates are exposed on a wooden rack at an angle of 45°. Test plates are cuts in the following size 12.5 × 7.5 × 0.16 cm. The chemical composition of the metals are : Aluminium - Commercial, Soft temper, Zinc - 98.5% purity, Pb (0.03% max), Cd (0.02% max) and Fe (0.01% max) and MS - C and Mn (0.5 max), S and P (0.05 max), Fe - rest.

Monthly and yearly corrosion rate of plates were carried out in 1995-96. All tests were carried out in duplicate and mean of the two values were taken. After exposure period, test plates were wrapped in plastic bags and brought to the laboratory for cleaning. Corrosion product on aluminium plates and zinc plates were derusted by as described¹³. Hudson used Clark's solution¹⁴ was used to remove the rust from mild-steel. Control specimen were used to determine the loss of metal in a cleaning solution and the final figures of the loss in weight of exposed specimens were corrected accordingly.

The salinity content (mg NaCl/sq.dm/month) in the air was assessed by the method described by Ambler and

Bain¹⁵. Measurement of sulphation rate was done by candle method. The lead peroxide method for monitoring SO₂ was developed in 1932 by the Department of Scientific and Industrial Research in England¹⁶.

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References

1. M. Morcillo, E. Almeida, B. Rosales, J. Uruchurtu and M. Marrocos, "Corrosion y Protection de Metales en la Atmosfera de Iberoamerica", Graficas Salve S.A., Spain, 1998.
2. ISO 9223, Corrosion of Metals and Alloys Corrosivity of Atmospheric Classification, 1992; V. Kucera, E. Mattsson in "Atmospheric Corrosion", ed. F. Mansfeld, Corrosion Mechanisms, Marcel Dekker, Inc, New York, 1987, 211.
3. S. Feliu, M. Morcillo and S. Feliu, *J. Corrosion Science*, 1993, **34**, 430; C. Arroyave, F. A. Lopez and M. Morcillo, *J. Corrosion Science*, 1995, **37**, 1751; F. Corvo and I. Leon, *Rev Iberoamericana de Corrosion y Protection*, 1988, **19**, 219.
4. R. K. Shah, "Pollution of Air and Water", University Granth Nirman Board, Ahmedabad, 1967, **2**, 182.
5. R. T. Vashi and H. G. Patel, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 1997, **13**, 343.
6. R. T. Vashi, G. M. Malek, V. A. Chempaneri and R. N. Patel, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 2002, **18**, 91.
7. R. T. Vashi and R. N. Patel, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 1996, **12**, 477.
8. B. Sanyal, A. N. Nandi, A. Natarajan and Bhadwar, *J. Sci. Indust. Res.*, 1959, **18-A**, 127.
9. J. C. Hudson and J. F. Stanners, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1959, **3**, 86.
10. F. W. Thomas and C. M. Davidson, *J. Air Pollut. Control Ass.*, 1961, **11**, 24.
11. J. D. Talati and B. M. Patel, Atmospheric Corrosion of Metals in Patan (N.G.), *Vidya*, 1967, **X-2**, 182.
12. A. R. Mendoza and F. Corvo, *Corrosion Science*, 2000, **42**, 1123.
13. L. Whitby, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1933, **23**, 527; E. G. Stroud, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1951, **1**, 93.
14. M. R. Foran, E. V. Gibbons and J. R. Wellington, "The Measurement of Atmospheric Sulfur Dioxide and Chlorides". Chem. In Canada, May 1958; ASTM Standards, Method for chemical cleaning after testing, 1978, **41-72**, 681.
15. H. R. Ambler and A. A. J. Bain, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1955, **5**, 437.
16. Department of Scientific and Industrial Research, The Investigation of Atmospheric Pollution, HMAO, London, 1933.